

Socio-Economic Effect of Fuel Subsidy Removal among Youth Involved in Small Scale Livestock Production in Ondo State, Nigeria
Ogungbemi O.I.

Department of Agricultural Science,

Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo

Corresponding address: folakemiibukun@gmail.com (08036679691)

ABSTRACT

The study assessed the socio-economic effect of removal of fuel subsidy on youth involved in small scale livestock production in Ondo State, Nigeria. Specifically, it described the demographic characteristics of the respondents; identified the types of small-scale livestock production activities involved in; determine the socio-economic effect of fuel subsidy and identified the coping strategies adopted. Structured questionnaire and interview schedule were utilized to collect data and data collected were summarized and presented using frequency tables, percentages and mean. A multi-stage sampling procedure was utilized to select 150 respondents for the study. Correlation analysis was used to establish relationship between demographic characteristics of respondents and effect of fuel subsidy removal. Results of analysis showed that mean age of respondents was 29.76 ± 2.74 years; respondents were involved in production of poultry (58.67%) and fish (51.33%); increase in cost of production (mean=2.90) and unemployment (mean=2.73) were socio-economic effect of removal of fuel subsidy on respondents; increased selling prices (70.00%) and diversification into non agri-businesses (58.67%) were the main coping strategies adopted by respondents. At $P \leq 0.01$, age ($r=0.413$) had a significant relationship with effect of fuel subsidy removal on respondents. The removal of fuel subsidy in Nigeria had a pronounced negative effect on youth involved in small scale livestock production in Ondo State and targeted interventions and support measures are essential to cushion these effects.

Keywords: Fuel subsidy removal, livestock production, socio-economic effect.

INTRODUCTION

Subsidy is a policy embarked upon, usually by the government, to make goods and services that are fundamental and important affordable for earners of low incomes in order to improve their living (Okoroh, 2024). According to Mohammed, Ahmed, and Adedeji (2020) government utilizes subsidies as a means of bringing economic effects down to reach the populace. Fuel subsidy is a deduction that the government provides on the price of petroleum products in order to make consumers pay less than the market prices that is prevalent in the market (Ovaga and Okechukwu, 2022). Fuel subsidy was first introduced in Nigeria in the year 1973 to make petroleum products more available and cheaper to generality of the populace and also to make more people benefit from them directly (Musa *et al.*, 2014). Another importance of fuel subsidy is to balance the fuel price when there is increased price of petroleum; as its price fluctuates in the international market.

According to Ozili and Arun (2022) in Nigeria, fuel subsidies were first introduced as a response to the increase in the price of petroleum in 1973. In 2012, the government suddenly removed fuel subsidy and the removal led to a serious protest which made the government reintroduced the fuel subsidy. In Nigeria, payment of fuel subsidy in Nigeria grew tremendously over the years; in 2022, it reached ₦4 trillion which amounted to 23 percent of the national budget (Ozili and Arun, 2022). Nigeria

could therefore, no longer maintain fuel subsidy and the government declared the removal in June 2023.

The effect of fuel subsidy removal has been argued to be positive, as well as negative in Nigeria as evidenced in literature which showed the double-edged effects of fuel subsidy. Omitogun, Longe, Muhammad, and Adekomi (2021), Adekunle and Oseni (2021), Asare, Reguant, Saab, and Sacchetto (2020) and Ozili and Arun, (2022) identified the benefits of fuel subsidy some of which included releasing financial resources for other sectors of the economy; enabling Nigeria's refineries to produce more products from petroleum; reducing dependency of the country on fuel that is imported; increasing employment; and channelling funds for the development of very important public infrastructure and therefore called for transparency in how the fuel subsidy removed is being administered. On the other hand, Ovaga and Okechukwu (2022), Omotosho (2019) and McCulloch, Moerenhout and Yang (2021) had argued that fuel subsidy removal has a negative effect on the general of the masses as a result of lack of dishonesty on the part of government in spending the proceeds saved from fuel subsidy removal in developing the nation's infrastructure.

Duntoye and Usman (2023) assessed the impact of fuel subsidy removal on agricultural production and asserted that barely one month after President Bola Ahmed Tinubu of Nigeria announced fuel subsidy

removal on 29th May, 2023, the average cost of food items in Nigeria increased by 53 percent, farm inputs increased by 71 percent, wages of farm labourers by increased by 149 percent and cost of transportation increased by 137 percent. Also, Kolawole, Adegun, and Adebo (2024) concluded that the short-term effect of oil subsidies removal the producers of poultry products hard as the cost of inputs (brooding charcoal, vaccines, drugs, feed, day old chicks and management) skyrocketed by 200 percent while the price of eggs only had a 100 per cent increase.

According to Mohammed, *et al.* (2020), the impact of fuel subsidy on livelihood in Nigeria was not largely favourable as the Nigerian economy had been designed to revolve around getting cheap petroleum products. The average Nigerian household relies on subsidised by-product of crude oil such as premium motor spirit, liquefied petroleum gas and automotive gas oil for domestic and commercial use. Idisi, Musa, Maduekwe, Isah, Idiege, Emmanuel, Ogunrinde and Atteh (2024) implied in the study of fuel subsidy removal on the socio-economic characteristics of households in Bwari, Abuja that fuel subsidy removal affected every member of the household irrespective of the age, marital status, sex, size of household and level of education in the buying of food items, medications, transportation, payment of educational fees and energy for cooking.

It is evident that studies are still on-going on the effect of the removal of fuel subsidy in Nigeria, especially as the effects are still biting and the common man is yet to access the palliative measures put in place to ameliorate these effects. This study is therefore carried out to increase the existing body of knowledge by investigating the socio-economic effect of fuel subsidy removal on the youth involved in small scale livestock production in Ondo State, Nigeria. To achieve this aim, this study was designed with the specific objectives to describe the personal characteristics of the respondents; identify the various types of livestock production activities involved in by the respondents; determine the socio-economic effect of fuel subsidy removal on the respondents and determine the coping strategies adopted by the respondents against fuel subsidy removal in the study area. One research hypothesis was formulated to test the relationship between personal characteristics of the respondents and the socio-economic effect of fuel subsidy removal.

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in Ondo State, Nigeria. The state is surrounded by Osun, Ogun, Ekiti, Kogi, Edo and Delta States and the Atlantic Ocean lies to the south. The state was established on

February 3rd, 1976 and Akure is the state capital. There are eighteen Local Government Areas (LGAs) and three senatorial districts in the state. Structured questionnaires and interview schedules were utilized to elicit data from the youth that were involved in small scale livestock production. A multi-stage sampling procedure was employed to select respondents for the study. At stage one, random selection of one LGA was done from each of the three senatorial districts, which are Ondo Central, Ondo South and Ondo North Senatorial District. The selected LGAs were: Ondo West, Owo and Okitipupa Local Government Areas. At stage two, random selection of five communities was done from the selected LGAs to give a total of fifteen communities that were sampled for the study. At stage three, ten youths were selected using snow ball sampling technique from the selected communities to make a total of one hundred and fifty (150) respondents for the study. Descriptive statistics (frequency counts, means and percentages) were used to describe the data collected and correlation analysis was used to determine the relationship between personal characteristics and socio-economic effect of fuel subsidy removal on the youth involved in small scale livestock production in Ondo State, Nigeria.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Personal characteristics of respondents

Results in Table 1 showed that the majority (66.67%) of the respondents were between 25 and 35 years, 13.33percent were below 25 years and 20.00percent were above 35 years. The average age of respondents was 29.76 ± 2.74 years. The implication of this is that the respondents were active youth in their prime and had the potential of carrying out their livestock production activities actively. This is in line with Adeyemi, Sobayo and Fadimu, (2012) who reported that a significant number of rural dwellers involved in poultry production were in their production age of 21 to 40 years and were still energetic. More than half (56.67%) of the respondents were male while 43.33 percent were female. The implication of this is that both male and female were involved in small scale livestock production in the study area.

Majority (65.33%) of the respondents were single while 34.67 percent were married. This showed that a large number of the respondents were not married and this could be as a result of young age or economic instability. The marital status of a person is expected to determine the extent of responsibility and the way in which he or she will distribute limited resources at his or her disposal (Mohammed *et al.*, 2020). Eighty percent of the respondents were Christians, 13.33 percent were Muslims, while 6.67 percent did not identify with

any religion. This showed the dominance of Christianity in the study area. This implies that change agents (NGOs and agricultural extension agents) can reach out to the youth through the church.

Thirty percent of the respondents had secondary school education, 33.33 percent had obtained or are undergoing training to obtain tertiary education; 16.00 percent had primary education, 14.67 percent had no formal education while 6.00 percent had obtained or are undergoing training to obtain post tertiary education. This indicated that majority of the respondents were literate. By implications high educational attainment will assist the respondents in accessing information on effective livestock production activities. The mean years of involvement of respondents in livestock production was 6.76 ± 2.74 years. More than half (62.0%)

claimed that the purpose of their livestock production is for home consumption only, while 38.0 percent claimed the production is for both commercial and home use. This showed that the respondents were small scale producers whose production was basically meant for home use while the little excess was sold.

Majority (69.33%) of the respondents had between 5 and 10 years, 18.67 percent had below 5 years and 12.00 percent had above 10 years of being involved in small scale livestock production activities in the study area. This agreed with Filusi *et al.* (2022) that 56.0 percent of youth involved in Youth in Agricultural Development Programme in Ekiti State had between 7 and 10 years of agricultural experience. This showed that the respondents were still young people who were just venturing into the poultry production business.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents based on personal demographic characteristics

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age (years)		
<25	20	13.33
25-35	100	66.67
>35	30	20.00
Mean	29.76 ± 2.74	
Gender		
Male	85	56.67
Female	65	43.33
Marital status		
Single	98	65.33
Married	52	34.67
Religion		
Christianity	120	80.00
Islam	20	13.33
No religious affiliation	10	6.67
Education Qualification		
Primary education	24	16.00
Secondary education	60	40.00
Tertiary education	57	38.00
Post tertiary education	9	6.00
Years of involvement in livestock production (years)		
<5	28	18.67
5-10	104	69.33
>10	18	12.00
Mean	6.76 ± 2.74	
Purpose of production		
Home consumption only	93	62.00
Commercial and home consumption	57	38.00

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Types of small-scale livestock production involved in by the respondents

Results in Table 2 revealed the various livestock being produced by youth in the study area. They were: poultry production (58.67%), fish production (51.33%), goat production (40.00%), rabbit

production (22.00%), pig production (18.67%), grasscutter production (17.33%), beekeeping (13.33%), and snail production (13.33%). Adeloje and Oke (2025) corroborated this finding that rearing of poultry and goats were the main

livestock being raised in the rural areas of Osun State.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents based on types of livestock production involved in

Various livestock production involved-in	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
Poultry production	88	58.67	1st
Fish production	77	51.33	2nd
Goat production	60	40.00	3rd
Rabbit production	33	22.00	4th
Pig production	28	18.67	5th
Grasscutter production	26	17.33	6th
Bee keeping	20	13.33	7th
Snail production	20	13.33	7th

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Socio-economic effect of fuel subsidy removal on respondents

As represented in Table 3, the result revealed the socio-economic effect of fuel subsidy removal on the respondents. The following were observed: increase in cost of livestock production (mean=2.90), unemployment (mean=2.73), lower socio-economic status (mean=2.72), reduced profit margin (mean=2.65), reduced purchasing power (mean=2.63) reduced participation in livestock production (mean=2.57), poor sales (mean=2.00), inability to pay school fees (mean=1.87), reduced contribution to family expenses (mean=1.57), reduced participation in social activities (mean=1.36), poor nutrition (mean=1.12) and rural-urban migration (mean=0.56).

The above finding agreed with Okoroh (2024) that farming households perceived increased food

prices (mean=3.5), increased price of farm produce (mean=3.2), reduced profitability of farming (mean=2.9), increased unemployment in the agricultural sector (mean=3.3), increased cost of production (mean=2.8) were perceived by farming households as the effects of fuel subsidy removal. Increase in pump prices of local petroleum products in Nigeria affect those activities that depend on petroleum products as the sources of energy. This implies that livestock producers have to spend more funds on transporting their products to the markets for sale. Also, Akinyemi *et al.* (2017) corroborated this that removal of fuel subsidies led to an escalation in the cost of production for farmers, which subsequently affected their overall welfare and income levels, which in turn led to decrease in agricultural productivity and profitability among farming households.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents based on socio-economic effect of fuel subsidy removal in the study area

Socio-economic effect	Mean	Rank
Increase in cost of livestock production	2.90	1 st
Unemployment	2.73	2 nd
Lower socio-economic status	2.72	3 rd
Reduced profit margin	2.65	4 th
Reduced purchasing power	2.63	5 th
Reduced participation in livestock production	2.57	6 th
Poor sales	2.00	7 th
Inability to pay school fees	1.87	8 th
Reduced contribution to family expenses	1.57	9 th
Reduced participation in social activities	1.36	10 th
Poor nutrition	1.12	11 th
Rural urban migration	0.56	12 th

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Grand mean = 2.06 Rating scale= High 3.00 Moderate = 2.00 Low 1.00 No effect = 0

Coping strategies adopted by respondents in dealing with effect of fuel subsidy

As represented in Table 4, the result revealed the coping strategies that the respondents put in place to mitigate the effect of removal of fuel subsidy. The following were observed: increasing selling

prices (70.00%), diversification into non-agri-businesses (58.67%), reduced livestock numbers (56.67%), diversification into other agri-businesses (43.33%), joining a cooperative (26.67%) and obtaining a loan (23.33%) were the coping strategies.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents by coping strategies

Coping strategies	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Increased selling prices	105	70.00
Diversification into non agri-businesses	88	58.67
Reduced livestock numbers	85	56.67
Diversification into other agri-businesses	65	43.33
Joining a cooperative	40	26.67
Obtaining a loan	35	23.33

Source: Field survey (2025)

Hypothesis Testing

Table 5 revealed the result of the Correlation Analysis between the personal characteristics of the respondents and socio-economic effect of fuel subsidy removal at $P \leq 0.01$. The results revealed that age ($r=0.413$) had significant and positive relationship with socio-economic effect of fuel subsidy removal. However, years spent in formal education ($r=0.233$), years of involvement ($r=0.$

231) and initial capital for investment ($r=0.246$) had no significant relationship. This implies that the older the youth are, the more biting the effect of fuel subsidy removal. Older youth in Ondo State are more likely to be married and have more family responsibilities, which consequently result in higher financial demands and are therefore more likely to be affected by fuel subsidy which had been stated to reduce purchasing power.

Table 5: Relationship between selected personal characteristics of respondents and socio-economic effect of fuel subsidy removal

Personal Characteristics	R	p-value	Decision
Age	0.413**	0.000	Significant
Years spent in formal education	0.233	0.623	Not Significant
Years involved in livestock farming	0.231	0.243	Not Significant
Initial capital invested	0.246	0.456	Not Significant

Source: Authors Computation, 2025 $P \leq 0.01$

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that the average age of respondents was 29.76 ± 2.74 years; 56.67 percent were male; 65.33 percent were single; 80.00 percent were Christians; 69.33 percent had post primary education and 62.00 percent produced livestock for home consumption only. The livestock produced by youth in the study area included poultry (58.67%), fish (51.33%) and goat (40.00%). The effect of fuel subsidy removal on the socio-economic status of the respondents were increased in cost of livestock production (mean=2.90), unemployment (2.73) and lower socio-economic status (2.72). The coping strategies that the respondents put in place to combat the effect of fuel subsidy removal were increasing selling prices (70.00%), diversification into non

agri-businesses (58.67%) and reducing livestock numbers (56.67%). Overall, the removal of fuel subsidies in Nigeria has a pronounced negative effect on the socio-economic status of youth involved in small-scale livestock production in Ondo State, Nigeria.

It was recommended that information about livestock production should be made available to the general public by the government, NGOs and private extension agencies. Youth should be targeted through the use of social media in information dissemination on livestock production. Targeted interventions by the government, NGOs and private extension agencies such as granting of loans to youth, allocation of land and supply of inputs (vaccines, drugs and feed) are needed to

prevent youth from abandoning livestock farming, unemployment and rural poverty. Furthermore strategic policy and support measures by the government are essential to cushion the negative effects of fuel subsidy in order to harness the

potential of youth in agricultural transformation. Youth are also encouraged to form cooperative associations for financial assistance and to organize collaborative efforts to reach out to agencies that will assist their livestock production activities.

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